

TE

WETR

Supplementary Figure 3–5 – Coverage plots of transposable elements (TEs), W-Elements and tandem repeats (WETR) and GC content across *S. mansoni* chromosomes. All data points plotted in the same windows as Figure 1 (1Mbp windows with 100kbp steps). Black dashed line indicates genomic mean and curved blue line implemented with the `geom_smooth` function to demonstrate trends across chromosomes.